

PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONAL VALEOLOGICAL COMPETENCES

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Abstract: In this article, opinions are presented about the pedagogical psychological and physiological aspects of the development of valeological competences of a person, and the article provides more detailed and extensive information on these aspects.

Key words: Valeological competence, pedagogical psychological and physiological aspects, healthy lifestyle, pedagogical aspect.

Self-contained pedagogical, psychological, and physiological processes are of great importance in the preservation and development of valeological or health of a person. These processes are interdependent and interacting networks.

Pedagogical aspect: This process is related to the provision of learning and development of knowledge and skills of the individual. Educational systems, teachers, learning materials, and learning methods play a major role in the valeological development of an individual. Along with other forms of learning, pedagogical methods play an important role in showing individual motivation, self-understanding, and self-development opportunities.

Psychological aspect: The psychological state of a person is one of the important aspects in his self-understanding, self-assessment with others and self-development. An individual's goals, motivations, self-discovery processes, emotions, and self-evaluation systems are important parts of this process.

Physiological aspect: Physical activity, proper nutrition, good sleep, stress reduction and protection from various functional diseases are related to the physiological aspects of the person. Physical activities, sports, principles and ongoing processes aimed at maintaining health are important in ensuring the physical development of an individual.

In ensuring the valeological development of the person, these three aspects should be used together. Using pedagogical methods, psychological concepts and physiological activities can be used together to give a person non-physiological experiences and increase his health and development processes. These processes have a great influence on each other and are a powerful self-fulfilling tool in the individual's self-development.

The development of personal valeological competence involves increasing the skills, knowledge and experience of the individual related to health and self-management. These competencies teach the individual how to maintain health, healthy eating, sports and physical activity, stress management and self-protection in accordance with external conditions.

The following ways can be used to learn and develop such competencies:

Access to information and learning: A person can obtain the necessary information for health, nutrition, active living, follow the news in this area, and use information sources and services.

Physical activities: Sports and movement provide physical development of a person and increase his energy. It is very important for a person to choose their own activities, participate in movement and sports in order to participate in public or other physical activities with other people.

Diet: A healthy and regular diet is very important for health. Learning the importance of personal nutrition and understanding the impact of a healthy diet is important in developing a person's valeological competencies.

Stress and self-management: Stress reduction, self-management in accordance with external conditions and coping with external factors should be learned. Meditation, yoga, mindfulness, and self-reflection techniques can help with this.

Self-evaluation and goal-setting: Understanding one's likes, goals and objectives, as well as self-evaluation and re-evaluation, are of great importance in the development of one's self.

Using and integrating these processes can be a good way to develop an individual's valeological competencies. It is important to allow for individual health and self-development through competitive and integrative methods.

Pedagogical, psychological and physiological processes are of great importance in maintaining and developing health. These processes include the physical and mental aspects of the individual and interact with him.

Pedagogical processes: These processes play an important role in providing the individual with the information he needs for self-development in learning and development. Learning systems, teaching methods, teachers and teaching materials are important in the maintenance and development of a person's health.

Psychological Processes: Psychological processes are very important in enhancing an individual's self-understanding, self-management, and motivation. Instead, focus on self-awareness, emotion management, stress management,

self-esteem, self-management techniques, self-expression, and connecting not only with yourself, but with others. is used.

Physiological Processes: Physiological processes are very important in physical development and health maintenance. These processes include proper nutrition, physical activities, sports, good sleep and principles. It is important to fight against specific physical harms and external conditions, to maintain oneself in accordance with external conditions, to develop one's physical abilities.

The integration of these together leads to increased health and development of the individual. When learning, psychological approaches and physical activities are used in harmony, the possibilities of self-development of the individual increase and lead him to maintain health. The combined use of these processes allows a person to use all approaches and greatly helps him in his self-development.

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